

Research Article

ANDA Filings in India: Insights from Industry Experts

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ABSTRACT

An Abbreviated New Drug Application (ANDA) is submitted to regulatory authorities for the approval of generic drugs. The regulatory requirements for ANDA approval vary across different regions. To obtain approval, an ANDA must demonstrate that the generic drug is bioequivalent to the reference listed drug, ensuring safety, efficacy, and quality in accordance with regulatory guidelines. The main objective of the study is to compare the critical factors, challenges and legal framework of various pharmaceutical industries in India for manufacturing and marketing of generic drugs. To analyze ANDA filings in India through insights from Industrial experts.

INTRODUCTION

The generic drugs manufacturing industry plays a crucial role in global healthcare by producing cost-effective alternatives to branded medications. These industries are vital in ensuring broader access to essential drugs, particularly in developing countries where healthcare affordability remains a significant concern. Generic drugs contain the same active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs), dosage forms, strengths, and routes of administration as their branded counterparts. Once the patent of a branded drug expires, generic manufacturers are permitted

to develop and market the equivalent version, provided it meets regulatory standards for quality, safety, and efficacy.

The rise of generic drug manufacturing is largely attributed to the need for affordable medications and the expiration of patents on blockbuster drugs. Countries like India have emerged as global leaders in generic drug production, supplying over 60% of the world's vaccines and 20% of generic medicines.

Generic drug manufacturers operate within a tightly regulated framework. Regulatory

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authorities like the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA), the European Medicines Agency (EMA), and India's Central Drugs Standard Control Organization (CDSCO) ensure that generic drugs meet stringent quality control and bioequivalence standards. Bioequivalence studies are crucial to demonstrate that a generic product performs in the same manner as the original brand-name drug. Only upon satisfying these requirements are generics approved for market entry.

Manufacturing generic drugs involves complex processes that require strict adherence to Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP). This includes maintaining controlled environments, employing high-precision equipment, and ensuring robust quality assurance mechanisms. Many generic manufacturers invest in vertically integrated operations, producing both active ingredients and finished formulations in-house. This integration helps in maintaining consistency, reducing costs, and improving supply chain control.

The generic drug industry also contributes significantly to pharmaceutical innovation, especially in areas such as drug delivery systems and formulation technology. While not involved in original drug discovery, many generic firms focus on developing complex generics, biosimilars, and value-added generics that improve patient compliance and therapeutic outcomes.

Challenges facing the generic drug manufacturing industry include pricing pressures, regulatory scrutiny, supply chain disruptions, and increasing competition from low-cost markets. However, rising global demand for affordable healthcare, the aging population, and the prevalence of chronic diseases continue to drive growth opportunities for generic manufacturers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study design

- Prevalence study was conducted to assess ANDA submission practices within the Indian pharmaceutical industry.
- Focused on five key pharmaceutical companies:
 1. Apex Laboratories Private Limited (Chennai, Tamil Nadu)
 2. Manufacturers Pharma Formulations Ltd (Chennai, Tamil Nadu)
 3. Itaan Pharma Private Limited (Karkapatla, Telangana)
 4. Kniss Pharmaceuticals (Chennai, Tamil Nadu)
 5. Theragen Lifescience (Chennai, Tamil Nadu)

Data Entry Format

- A structured questionnaire was designed to gather key insights, focusing on:
 - Critical factors in assessing ANDA submissions.
 - Balancing safety, efficacy, and timely approval.
 - Harmonizing global standards.
 - Significant hurdles.
 - Cost implications and market accessibility.
 - Strategic approaches for successful ANDA filings.

- Legal frameworks, exclusivity provisions, and regulatory challenges.
- Impact of ANDA submissions on patient outcomes.

Inclusion Criteria

- Industry professionals responsible for Regulatory affairs from the specified pharmaceutical industries were included.

Exclusion Criteria

- Individuals not associated with the mentioned industries were excluded from the study.
- Pharmaceutical industries that specialize solely in the packaging of generic drugs were excluded from the study.

Data Collection Process

- A structured questionnaire was distributed to industry professionals, and responses were systematically collected.
- Data gathered encompassed their experiences, expertise, and strategic recommendations for streamlining the ANDA submission process.

Data Analysis

- The qualitative methods were employed to evaluate the responses.
- The analysis focused on identifying key trends, challenges, and strategic approaches based on expert opinions.
- Findings were systematically organized and presented in a tabular format for clear interpretation and comparison.

RESULT

Apex Laboratories Pvt. Ltd.

Apex Laboratories Pvt. Ltd. is a leading pharmaceutical company based in Chennai, India, renowned for pioneering the introduction of zinc-based formulations in the Indian market. Established in 1978, Apex has grown into one of India's top 50 pharmaceutical companies, specializing in oral solids, oral liquids, and topical dosage forms. Its flagship brand, Zincovit, has become a household name in the multivitamin and mineral supplement segment.

Manufacturers Pharma Formulations

Manufacturers Pharma Formulations is a pharmaceutical company located in Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India. Established in 1991, the company specializes in manufacturing of pharmaceutical intermediate, special chemicals, impurities and active pharmaceutical ingredient (API).

Itaan Pharma Private Limited

Itaan Pharma Private Limited is a pharmaceutical company specializing in injectable formulations. It is established in 2020. It is located in Telangana, Andhra Pradesh. Their leadership team brings decades of specialized experience in sterile product development and commercialization, ensuring that every aspect of our operations aligns with the latest global regulatory requirements – from early-phase formulation to regulatory submission and commercial-scale manufacturing. Their unwavering commitment to scientific rigor and attention to product-specific details enables us to develop high-quality injectable therapies that meet critical patient needs. They optimize the product lifecycle by integrating technical expertise

with strategic commercialization, ensuring efficiency, scalability, and market success.

Kniss Laboratories Pvt. Ltd

Kniss Laboratories Pvt. Ltd. is a pharmaceutical company located in Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India. Established in 1989, the company specializes in manufacturing and marketing a wide range of pharmaceutical and nutraceutical products, including vitamins, anti-cold preparations, pain management solutions, protein food supplements, antioxidants, sleep-inducing agents, antimalarials, anti-epileptics, and digestive enzymes.

Theragen Lifesciences Pvt Ltd

Theragen Lifesciences Pvt Ltd is a pharmaceutical research and development organization based in Chennai, India. Established in May 2017 by a team of medical professionals, the company aims to become a leading and differentiated entity in the global healthcare industry.

To understand the practical challenges and strategies in ANDA filings in India, we gathered insights from industry experts at Apex Pharma Private Limited, Manufacturers Pharma Formulation, Itaan Pharma Private Limited, and Kniss Pharmaceuticals. Their responses offer a real-world perspective on regulatory hurdles, approval timelines, and best practices. The table below summarizes their key insights

Table 1: Comparison of ANDA filings in Pharmaceutical Industries through insights from industry experts

Parameters	Apex Pharma Private Limited	Manufacturers Pharma Formulation	Itaan Pharma Private Limited	Kniss Pharmaceuticals	Theragen Lifescience
Critical factors in assessing ANDA submissions	Meeting stringent requirements	Potency, efficacy and impurity profile	Pharmaceutical quality and CMC data	Bioequivalence data	CMC compliance
Balancing safety, efficacy, and timely approval	Efficient review process	Prioritizing public health needs.	Risk based assessment	Effective trial and post marketing surveillance	By reviewing the reports
Challenges faced in harmonizing global standards	Language	Limited resources	Geographies specification and test methods	Robust clinical trials	Compendial requirements
Significant hurdles in preparing ANDA submissions	Maintenance of stability and submissions of BA/BE Studies	Conducting BA/BE studies	Marketing specifications and STPs	Technical and scientific differences	Bio-equivalence part
Impact on cost and timeline of drug development	Delays due to varying review process	Extended timelines	Additional studies	Potential Financial burden	Extended timelines
Local regulation influence in strategy	Maintaining valid GMP and administrative documents	Obtaining license for BA/BE studies	Maintaining WHO GMP license	Market access and Legal advice	By providing the incentives
Patents laws and exclusivity provisions	Filing ANDA with paragraph IV certifications	Patent protection for molecules and formulation	Filing ANDA with paragraph IV certifications	Local market access	paragraph IV certifications

Legal challenges faces	Patent related issues	Time interval for obtaining NOC for BA/BE studies	NCE and paragraph IV filing	Maintenance of standards from USFDA	Meeting the facility up to the required standard
Impacted patient outcome by regulatory delay	Frequent submissions of same products	Public health challenges	Delayed access of critical product	Survival, symptoms, QoL	Affordability
Legal framework for drug availability	CFR and National institute of health	Compulsory licensing	Hatch-Waxman Act	Patent evergreening	Market exclusivity

DISCUSSION

While regulatory agencies provide structured pathways for ANDA approvals, pharmaceutical companies often encounter practical challenges that are not fully addressed by regulations. To understand these challenges, interviews were conducted with experts from Apex Pharma Private Limited, Manufacturers Pharma Formulation, Itaan Pharma Private Limited, and Kniss Pharmaceuticals. Their insights highlight key obstacles related to approval timelines, bioequivalence studies, post-marketing surveillance, and patent regulations.

1. Approval Timelines and Delays

Regulatory agencies set clear timelines for ANDA approvals, but in practice, companies often experience delays due to repeated queries, additional documentation requirements, and evolving guidelines.

"The official approval timeline may be 12 months, but in reality, it often takes much longer due to back-and-forth communication with regulators." – (Industry Expert, Apex Pharma Private Limited)

The study found that actual approval times vary across jurisdictions:

- USA (FDA): ~18 months

- EU (EMA): ~12 months
- India (CDSCO): ~12+ months, often delayed

Industry professionals noted that such delays increase development costs and postpone market entry, making it difficult for companies to plan their product launches efficiently.

2. Challenges in Bioequivalence Studies

Bioequivalence (BE) studies are required for ANDA approvals, but differences in study design, acceptance criteria, and stability requirements create difficulties for manufacturers.

"We often have to repeat bioequivalence studies for different regulatory agencies, even when the results are already well-established." – (Industry Expert, Manufacturers Pharma Formulation)

The study identified variations in BE requirements across regions:

- USA (FDA): 80.00–125.00% CI for C_{max} and AUC
- EU (EMA): Stricter criteria for highly variable drugs
- China (NMPA): More stringent bioequivalence parameters

- India (CDSCO): Similar to FDA but with local study requirements

Experts emphasized that these inconsistencies increase costs and delay approvals, as companies must conduct separate studies to meet region-specific criteria.

3. Post-Marketing Surveillance and Compliance Issues

Post-marketing surveillance (PMS) ensures drug safety after approval, but industry professionals noted challenges in compliance, data reporting, and enforcement.

"While post-marketing surveillance is mandatory, follow-ups and enforcement vary, making it difficult to predict regulatory expectations." – (Industry Expert, Kniss Pharmaceuticals)

This aligns with findings from the study:

- USA (FDA – FAERS) and EU (EMA – GVP): Well-established PMS systems
- India (PvPI) and China's PMS system: Underreporting and inconsistent enforcement

Experts pointed out that inconsistent pharmacovigilance reporting and lack of standardized digital systems limit the effectiveness of post-marketing surveillance efforts.

4. Patent Barriers and Market Access Challenges

Patent exclusivity and legal challenges often delay generic drug approvals, even after regulatory requirements are met.

"Even after successfully filing an ANDA, patent-related delays prevent timely market entry." – (Industry Expert, Itaan Pharma Private Limited)

The study found that:

- USA (Hatch-Waxman Act): Grants 180-day exclusivity to first generic filers, delaying competitors.
- China: Implements a patent linkage system, preventing generic approvals before innovator patents expire.
- EU: Follows a decentralized process, requiring additional national-level approvals.

Industry professionals highlighted that such legal barriers reduce competition and delay patient access to affordable medicines.

5. Industry Challenges and the Need for Regulatory Adaptation

Comparing industry insights with regulatory frameworks reveals that while agencies aim to streamline ANDA approvals, companies still face delays, inconsistencies in bioequivalence standards, challenges in post-marketing surveillance, and legal hurdles due to patent exclusivity.

These insights highlight the need for regulatory adaptation to:

- Reduce approval delays by ensuring more predictable and transparent review processes.
- Align bioequivalence study requirements to minimize unnecessary duplication.
- Improve post-marketing surveillance enforcement for better drug safety monitoring.
- Balance patent protection with generic competition to enhance market access.

By addressing these industry concerns, regulatory agencies can improve the efficiency of ANDA

approvals, ensuring faster availability of cost-effective generic medicine

CONCLUSION

Generic drug manufacturers play a critical role in making healthcare more affordable by providing cost-effective alternatives to brand-name drugs. These drugs undergo rigorous testing and regulation to ensure they meet the same safety and efficacy standards as their branded counterparts, with any differences typically limited to excipients. A comprehensive understanding of regulatory guidelines is crucial for pharmaceutical companies and researchers to navigate the complex regulatory landscape effectively. Strengthening this knowledge will contribute to the global availability of high-quality generic medicines, ultimately improving healthcare affordability and access.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

The authors have no conflicts of interest regarding this investigation.

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